

Mixed mode criterion for discrete crack propagation through RC shear zones

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Abstract

Shear load is considered as one of the most important actions in the assessment of reinforced concrete structures. Over the last two decades, significant progress has been made in numerical modelling, with a focus on crack propagation in quasi-brittle materials. It is now generally accepted that complex interaction effects governing the shear crack propagation in RC members can only be captured using discrete crack models. The open question remains as to the correct description of the fracture process zone under mixed-mode loading, which would be generally applicable for discrete crack models. Besides the finite-element method, an interesting class of models have emerged in the last decade that use simplifying kinematic assumptions with the goal to derive analytical solution of the governing equilibrium equations. These models are particularly important for improving the engineering assessment rules for shear zones. A similar approach is being proposed in this paper to evaluate the crack propagation and orientation in a shear span. The model uses a novel kinematic approach for evaluating the crack propagation of a shear crack along with a simple crack orientation criterion. Furthermore, the attained maximum shear capacity and the contributions from dowel and aggregate action are reported to see the reliability of the model and a glimpse on the future aspects of the model are also shown. The model will be validated in the long run and the developed criterion will be applied within a novel incremental semi-analytical model of the crack propagation process, efficiently capturing the shear zone kinematics and equilibrium.

Keywords: *Mixed mode loading, Principal tensile stress, Shear crack propagation*

1. Introduction

Shear load is one of the most important actions for the assessment of Reinforced Concrete (RC) Structures. RC slabs and beams without shear reinforcement are examples of structural members that can fulfil the need for efficient construction. Significant research has been done already to study the shear behaviour. A consensus on the existence of different interacting effects of material behaviour (i.e. aggregate interlock, dowel action, etc.) is attained but the question on the significance of the roles of these individual effects within a shear failure process is still under discussion. This question provides an opportunity to look for a new kinematic procedure that can contribute to this scientific conversation by pointing out the importance of individual effects within a critical shear region. The primary factor in the propagation of a shear crack is the existence of stable crack growth before the crack reaches its critical length (Chengsheng 1990). Many models are developed so far to explicitly address the elementary effects controlling the shear failure process. Shear Crack Propagation Theory put forward by Classen (Classen 2020) proposes a novel shear crack propagation model considering biaxial stresses combining Hillerborg approach (Hillerborg 1976) for cohesive crack with Kupfer's fracture criterion (Kupfer 1969). With the advancement in computing processors in the recent past decade, new models have emerged that are more efficient in predicting the critical crack in a shear span. The paper also contributes to this direction by looking into the efficiency of simulating a crack by this novel kinematic approach.

2. Crack propagation model

2.1. Shear zone kinematics

The proposed kinematics calculate the geometry of the discrete shear crack and the entire loading process. The model takes the initial crack position as an input parameter and simulates the complete crack geometry based on small increments. A simple graphical explanation to the kinematics is shown in Figure 1 (a) where three segments are highlighted to depict the overall step by step incremental procedure. The first segment represents a crack whereas the second part exhibits the fracture process zone that is represented by a continuous curve i.e. spline or piece-wise linear geometry. The length of the fracture process section is L^{fps} with an orientation ψ with respect to the vertical direction z . The upper part represents the uncracked zone x_U . The coordinates of the process zone segment x_{ak}^{fps} given in (1) is implicitly considered to be in the state of peak tensile stress with $a \in (0,1)$ denoting the dimension index, k depicting the incremental index and n is the index of the nodal coordinate. So, the position of the tip of the fracture process zone can be expressed by:

$$x_{ak}^{fps} = x_{an}^{tip} + L^{fps} \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \psi \\ \cos \psi \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. (a) Beam crack kinematics (b) Constitutive laws (c) Equilibrium

where, x_{an}^{tip} depicts the tip of the pre-existing crack. The kinematics of the section assume that the right side of the shear zone rotates relatively to the fixed left side around an unknown center of rotation x_{ak}^{rot} . The horizontal position of the center of rotation is considered aligned to the horizontal location of fracture process zone segment (i.e. x_{0k}^{fps}). Therefore:

$$x_{ak}^{rot} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{0k}^{fps} \\ x_{1k}^{rot} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where, x_{1k}^{rot} represents the vertical point of the center of rotation which is initially taken as $H/2$.

2.1.1. Crack extension criterion

Another important aspect of the crack propagation model is the crack extension criterion. It is assumed that the opening w at the tip of the crack is equivalent to the critical width w_{cr} which is written as:

$$w_{cr} = \frac{f_t}{E_c} L_c \quad (3)$$

where, f_t , E_c , L_c represent the tensile strength of concrete, modulus of elasticity of concrete and the characteristic length, respectively. As already stated, the model takes the initial crack position as an input parameter. Furthermore, the length of the fracture process zone segment (L^{fps}) is also defined as input. Based on these assumptions the model calculates the geometry of the propagating crack by updating the position of the fracture process zone segment x_{ak}^{fps} and the previous crack tip. By explicitly

relating the tensile concrete strength to a local kinematic variable w_{cr} it is possible to find a closed form solution for the rotation angle ψ corresponding the prescribed crack extension. With this kinematically described state, the local strain and crack opening profiles along the shear zone ligament become available and can be used as input in the constitutive laws of components acting within the cross section.

2.2. Cross-sectional equilibrium

To find the instantaneous center of rotation and a crack propagation direction for a prescribed extension of a crack, the cross-sectional equilibrium condition is constructed by evaluating all the relevant stress components as indicated in Figure 1 (c). Both horizontal and vertical stress components are considered, including the contributions from uncracked concrete section, reinforcement bridging and dowel action, concrete softening in the fracture process zone and, aggregate interlock between edges of the localized crack. The constitutive laws applied for the individual contributions to the cross-sectional equilibrium conditions are briefly summarized in the following paragraphs.

2.2.1. Dowel action

The dowel effect refers to the ability of the reinforcement bars in bending to transfer transverse forces through the crack, thus be activated if the longitudinal reinforcement follows a shear movement (Cavagnis 2017). The development of tensile stresses in concrete is essential for the activation of dowel action in flexural reinforcement. Furthermore, this evolution of vertical tensile stresses which potentially originates the delamination crack is needed for the equilibrium of shear forces in the reinforcement. The dowelling action can still occur even with the growth of this delamination crack due to the reason that the tensile stresses develop again at the tip of delamination crack (Ruiz 2015). Baumann and Rusch model is used here as constitutive law for dowel action (Baumann and Rusch 1970). So, the total shear force due to dowel action reads:

$$V_{d \max} = 1.64 b_n \phi f_c^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4)$$

where, b_n is the clear width of the beam given by $B - n \phi$. Here, ϕ , n , B , f_c represents diameter of bar, number of bars, width of beam, compressive strength of concrete, respectively. With reference to Shear Crack Propagation Theory (SCPT) the dowel force is obtained as (Classen 2020):

$$V_{da} = \begin{cases} V_{d \max} \frac{s}{0.05} \left(2 - \frac{s}{0.05} \right) & \text{for } s \leq 0.05 \text{ mm} \\ V_{d \max} \frac{2.55 - s}{2.5} \geq 0 & \text{for } s > 0.05 \text{ mm} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. (a) Dowel action test setup from Baumann and Rusch Experiments (Baumann and Rusch 1970), (b) cross section of a beam, (c) Dowel force for the numerical simulation

where s is the slip displacement at steel reinforcement. A simple constitutive law for dowel action adopting Baumann and Rusch model used for numerical simulation of the assumed beam is plotted in Figure 2 (c) whereas Figure 2 (a), (b) shows the test setup for the Dowel action and the cross-section properties of the simulated beam.

2.2.2. Aggregate interlock

The displacement of crack faces with respect to each other is termed as aggregate interlock (Walraven 1980). With reference to the experiments conducted (Jacobsen 2012), cracks are found to propagate in

a vertical manner initially due to the reason that the opening is more pronounced at the crack tip (Huber 2016). The corresponding normal stresses due to these openings become significantly lower than the shear stresses in the region of aggregate interlocking mechanism due to the governing slip displacement (Jacobsen 2012). Therefore, the shear stresses are prominent in the region of aggregate interlock. However, when the crack surfaces slide against each other the aggregate interlock with the cement matrix of the opposite surface results in increase of shear strength. The aggregate interlock model proposed by Bazant (Bazant 1980) and later refined by Gambarova (Gambarova 1983) is used here as a constitutive law to account for shear stresses due to aggregate interlock acting at a crack. Therefore,

$$\sigma_{ag} = -0.62 \sqrt{w} \frac{r}{(1+r^2)^{0.25}} \tau_{ag} \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{ag} = \tau_0 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{2w}{d_g}} \right) r \frac{a_3 + a_4 \|r\|^3}{1 + a_4 r^4} \quad (7)$$

where, $r = s/w$, $\tau_0 = 0.25 f_c$, $a_3 = 2.45/\tau_0$ and $a_4 = 2.44(1 - 4/\tau_0)$. σ_{ag} , τ_{ag} , and d_g represents the normal stresses, shear stresses due to aggregate interlock and size of aggregate respectively and s , w , f_c are slip, horizontal opening and compressive strength of concrete.

Figure 3. (a) Aggregate interlock mechanism, (b) Shear stresses due to aggregate interlocking, (c) Normal stresses due to aggregate interlocking

Figure 3 depicts the shear and normal stresses resulting from the constitutive law adopted for the numerical simulation of an assumed reinforced concrete beam. It shows that as the horizontal opening increases the shear stress reduces. Moreover, a similar trend is observed for the normal stresses where the negative value is highlighting compression.

2.2.3. Crack bridging action of the reinforcement

A constant bond slip law is being used in the simulation and the force at the steel reinforcement is assumed as a square root function of a pull-out approximation. Hence, it reads:

$$P = \sqrt{2w\tau E_f A_f p} \quad (8)$$

here, w , τ , E_f , A_f , p are horizontal crack opening, bond stress, modulus of elasticity, area, and perimeter of steel reinforcement, respectively.

2.2.4. Concrete softening during strain localization in the fracture process zone

Cracked concrete tends to transfer tensile stresses for small crack openings. The constitutive law to account this softening behaviour of concrete is written as:

$$\sigma_{fpz} = f_t \exp \left[-f_t \left(\frac{w - w_{cr}}{G_f} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

where, G_f represents the fracture energy which is taken as a constant value obtained by Mari and Cladera approach (Mari and Cladera 2015)

$$G_f = 0.028 f_c^{0.18} d_g^{0.32} \quad (10)$$

2.2.5. Concrete behaviour in compression

The concrete behaviour is assumed to be ideally plastic in compression (Figure 1 (b)).

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} -f_c & \text{for } \frac{E_c w}{L_c} < -f_c \\ \frac{E_c w}{L_c} & \text{for } w \leq w_{cr} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

2.2.6. Shear stress at crack tip

The shear contribution in continuous concrete is acquired by realizing that the integral of the shear stresses over the cross section must be equal to the global shear force V . Normal stress distribution along the longitudinal axis of members under concentrated loads is linear due to which parabolic shape function is used to describe the shear stress state at crack tip. So,

$$\tau = az^2 + bz + c \quad (12)$$

where, a,b,c can be equated from the boundary condition i.e. zero stress at the top fiber of the compression zone whereas maximum shear distribution acts at the center of rotation (see Figure 4 (c,d)).

2.3. Crack orientation criterion

A simple approach of principal stress directions is used here to evaluate the orientation of the shear crack.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = PDP^{-1} \quad (13)$$

where, P , D represents principal stresses and eigen values, respectively. By using this simple approach, angle of crack propagation can be simulated efficiently (Figure 4). As the stress state is already known in a beam, therefore, this approach of principal stress direction can be adopted to simulate orientation of a shear crack (Figure 4(a)).

$$\sigma_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x & \tau \\ \tau & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_t & \tau \\ \tau & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Here, σ_x is the normal stress that depends on the tensile strength of concrete for propagation whereas shear stress τ is obtained from the parabolic shape function (12). Based on the known state of stress at the crack tip an attempt has been made in this paper to evaluate the crack orientation of a shear crack. Hence, the angle of crack propagation can be obtained simply from principal stresses as (Figure 4 (b)):

$$\psi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_1} \right) \quad (15)$$

Figure 4. (a) Stress state within the shear zone of a beam, (b) Crack tip orientation criterion (c) Shear stress at crack tip when crack is below center of rotation, (d) Shear stress at crack tip when crack has propagated into compression zone

In the present state, the crack parallel stress denoted as T in Figure 4 (a) is not added for the evaluation of the orientation of the propagating crack and will be added during further development of the model in the near future.

2.4. Shear capacity

The model simulates the whole nonlinear load-deflection response of a single crack. The shear capacity for this crack can be attained by picking up the value of maximum load from the load deflection curve. This procedure is continued for different crack positions and the profile of the maximum shear capacity is plotted (Section 3).

3. Verification studies

A simply supported beam is assumed here for performing simulations from the proposed crack propagation model (Table 1). The results show various advantages of this novel approach which are highlighted in this section. The model can simulate the stresses in a crack and is able to depict the history of stress distributions throughout the crack profile until failure. The stress states for three different positions along the height of propagating crack located at the center of the beam are shown in Figure 5 (b). The stress at crack tip is illustrated with red line. The stress profile visualizes all positions i.e. crack tip, fracture process zone and center of rotation.

Another important aspect of the model is its ability to show force distributions along the history of the propagating crack. To explain the clear picture, three different crack positions are selected i.e. 0.1L, 0.5L, 0.9L (Figure 6 (a)). The corresponding results are plotted for two shear zone actions (aggregate interlock and dowel action). The obtained results are shown here for the same three vertical positions of the crack discussed above. A significant rise in the force contributions can be seen for both 0.1L and 0.5L crack but the spike in force contributions for 0.9L is not as remarkable as observed for other two cracks. This behaviour of the maximum force contributions is expected to improve by the incorporation of the crack propagation criterion (Section 4) and further effects i.e. cantilever action.

The efficiency of models analysing shear crack propagation are crucial for their applicability in engineering practice. This computational complexity of the model is demonstrated in Figure 7 (a) where the crack located at the center of the beam is analysed. Figure 7 (a) illustrates the time taken for the complete simulation against number of simulated crack propagation steps. This example shows that 140 crack segments are obtained within 25 seconds indicating a relatively fast convergence to equilibrium. The corresponding load deflection curve is plotted in Figure 7 (b).

Maximum dowel action and aggregate force contributions are also plotted to contribute towards ongoing discussion of the role or significance of individual components contributing towards shear strength. The performed study shows that for the chosen constitutive laws, the effect of the dowel action is slightly higher than the aggregate interlock closer to the loading point but this trend changes and it appears that aggregate interlock is governing contributor towards shear capacity as we move away towards the support (Figure 8 (c)).

Table 1. Material properties for simulation studies

Shear Span (mm)Shear Span (mm)	Cross -section (mm x mm)	Compressive strength of concrete (N/mm ²)	Dia of aggregate (mm)	No. of bars (no.)	Bar dia (mm)	Yield strength of steel (N/mm ²)
3850	250 x 600	33.3	16	2	28	713

Figure 5. (a) Simulated crack path (b) History tracing of stress profiles

The maximum shear capacity is plotted in Figure 8 (b). The shear capacity tends to increase towards the support. Still, this result is only preliminary as the crack propagation criterion discussed in Section 4 and eventually further effects, like cantilever action are not yet added to the model. Enriched with these model components, more detailed studies can be performed and validated based on experimental results. The shown simulations are performed for 9 different crack positions but only three different locations are highlighted here for clarity (Figure 8(a)).

The model is also able to simulate any experimental result such as the bending moment-crack opening

Figure 6. (a) History tracing of a simulated crack path (b) Maximum aggregate contribution history tracing, (c) Maximum dowel action contribution

Figure 7. (a) No. of segments - calculation time relationship (b) Load deflection curve (c) Bending moment crack opening relationship (d) Horizontal force contribution

Figure 8. (a) Simulated crack paths (b) Maximum shear capacity, (c) Dowel and aggregate force contributions

relationship as shown below in Figure 7 (c). The result of bending moment crack opening relationship shows a realistic behaviour. The horizontal steel force (Figure 7 (d)) from the model shows a realistic trend i.e. the force contribution is decreasing towards the support. This action is needed to improve further in the model for the state at which high crack parallel stress and a crack orientation criterion (i.e. maximum principal stress theory) develops in the compression zone.

4. Future aspects

The prepared discrete crack framework is able to incorporate further model components. A particular import is the refinement in the crack-propagation criterion that can account for the two-dimensional stress state in the fracture process zone.

4.1. Maximum principal stress theory (MPST)

Over the past two decades, fracture mechanics has been used extensively to study the quasi-brittle behaviour of materials such as concrete, rock and ceramics. Multiple theories exist in the literature to describe brittle failure under combined effect of tensile and shear loading in fracture mechanics but the

focus here is limited towards Maximum Principal Stress Theory (MPS) that can be used for the visualization of shear crack orientation (Smith 2001). According to this theory, crack growth will take place for an in-plane mixed mode along the direction for which the initial normal stress across the possible crack path is tensile, principal, and maximum (Bazant 1997). The theory evaluates the stresses in the vicinity of crack tip from the known far field stress state. The external stresses at a point in the finite element and along the crack are shown in Figure 9 and represented as:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} (1-\eta)\bar{\sigma} & \eta\bar{\sigma} \\ \eta\bar{\sigma} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Here, $\bar{\sigma}$ represents the far field stress state whereas η represents a coefficient which acts as a switch whose value range from zero to one to constitute the cases from pure tension to pure shear. The far field stress is depicting the stress state at a point in an element, but transformation is required to convert this stress state along the crack for evaluating the stresses within the propagating crack using the Westergaard stress functions. Hence,

$$R_{kl}^{\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\beta & -\sin\beta \\ \sin\beta & \cos\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{kl}^{\beta} = R_{ki}^{\beta} \bar{\sigma}_{ij} R_{jl}^{\beta} \quad (18)$$

Figure 9. (a) Lay out of far field stresses (b) Stress orientation on the tip of the crack according to Westergaard Stress Function

where, R_{kl}^{β} is the transformation matrix along initial crack inclination angle β whereas Equation 18 shows the transformed stress field along the crack. In order to obtain the stress profile at the tip of the crack, Westergaard stress function is used which requires the stress state to be converted into the stress intensity factors i.e. K_I , K_{II} which depicts the mode I, mode II stress intensity factors respectively. The reason for using stress intensity factors is because they portray the complete severity of the stress state at the crack tip by taking into account the transformed far field stresses and the length of the crack. (Irwin 1997). So,

$$K_I = \sqrt{\pi a} \bar{\sigma}_{11}^{\beta}; K_{II} = \sqrt{\pi a} \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{\beta} \quad (19)$$

Positive sign of stress intensity factors highlights tension while the negative values show compression.

4.2. Stress profile at crack tip including T-stress

The stress profile around crack tip conceptualized by Westergaard stress function (Westergaard 1939) and simplified by Irwin using Airy stress functions is used in MPST based on an assumption that the material is isotropic. Westergaard gave the solution of stress field in an infinite plate consisting of a crack in complex numbers. However, this equation of complex numbers showing stress at crack tip is written simply here as:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\beta}(\rho) = \frac{[K_I S_{ij}^I(\theta) + K_{II} S_{ij}^{II}(\theta)]}{\sqrt{2\pi\rho}} + T \delta_{i1} \delta_{j1} \quad (20)$$

where $S_{ij}^I(\theta)$, $S_{ij}^{II}(\theta)$ are the angular functions obtained from Irwin's approximation and are discussed in detail elsewhere (Bazant 1997). William and Ewing observed discrepancy in between the results obtained by MPST and experiments with large difference occurring at small loading angles. One of the

reasons for this discrepancy was T-stress which is also known as crack parallel stress (Williams 1972). Hence, crack parallel stress is added into Equation 20. The crack parallel stress can be evaluated from stress difference method by the difference of stresses acting along the crack (Yang 1999):

$$T = \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{\beta} - \bar{\sigma}_{11}^{\beta} \quad (21)$$

Figure 9 (b) shows the stress field from Westergaard functions to explain the stress state around the crack. To apply the maximum principal stress criterion for crack propagation transformation of the stresses into polar coordinates is required.

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\theta}(\theta, \rho) = R_{ki}^{\theta} \tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^{\beta} R_{jl}^{\theta} \quad (22)$$

where,

$$R_{kl}^{\theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & -\sin\theta \\ \sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

Now the crack propagation angle can be attained by following the principal condition of MPST which states that the stresses are principal i.e.:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{12}^{\theta} = 0 \quad (24)$$

With this condition, crack propagation angle θ at the tip of the crack can be attained if the global stress states, inclination, and length of the previous crack is already known. With this proposed state of stress at a point in the crack, studies are performed to visualize how the crack will propagate according to Maximum Principal Stress Theory for three cases (i.e. pure tension, mixed mode and pure shear) without the inclusion of T-stresses for simplicity (Figure 10). The studies show that the propagating crack can be attained simply as:

$$\psi = \theta + \beta \quad (25)$$

Figure 10. (a) Crack propagation for the case of pure tension (b) Crack propagation for the case of mixed mode (c) Crack propagation for the case of pure shear

5. Conclusions

The aim of the paper is to contribute to the ongoing discussion of the role or significance of different actions within a shear zone towards shear capacity by using a novel approach. Based on the approach used, following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The model can show the history of stress profiles, force contributions due to each individual actions and maximum shear capacity.

2. The model is extremely efficient and can simulate many segments in seconds.
3. The kinematics shows reasonable results, and it is expected that with the addition of crack propagation criteria and crack parallel stress, the results may improve further.
4. It has been found out that in the initial positions of the crack, dowel action contribution is more than the aggregate interlock, but aggregate interlock contribution increases significantly as we move towards support.
5. The horizontal force at steel acting throughout the beam and the bending moment-crack opening relationship show reasonable behaviours.
6. Based on the results obtained by Maximum principal stress theory for a simple case, it can be stated that it can be used as a crack orientation criterion for the propagation of the shear crack.

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